

SUBSYSTEM FOR SYNCHRONIZATION AND ANALYSIS OF ARDUINO PLATFORM SENSORS DATA

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ABSTRACT

Smart energy systems use Arduino sensors data as the main part. Communication between the Arduino platform sensors and the server is provided by the developed subsystem of messages and serialization to a byte stream. The developed subsystem provides a flexible data transmission mechanism based on the RUDP protocol. This allows us to make the delivery's reliability and confirms packets of specific sensors data, better than systems with TCP or UDP protocols. For example, a system based on TCP protocol can synchronize messages frequently, therefore the acknowledgment mechanism loads network bandwidth. The reliability of a system with UDP will not be provided so UDP requires additional checks. RUDP protocol solves these problems so it was used in our work. Subsystem requires the usage of a Wi-Fi access point from the agent side. Dynamic calculation of the round-trip-time (RTT) was implemented. This value is significant to calculate the time to receive confirmation from the server for each message that needs to be sent or resent. This reduces the number of network errors of data retransmissions and further reduces the load on bandwidth as a result. So, the developed subsystem provides quickly and reliably delivering of sensors data than before. The subsystem can be used in a smart house.

Keywords: sensor data synchronization, agent, Arduino board, UDP usage problems, packet delivery reliability, RUDP

INTRODUCTION

The efficiency of client-server applications ensures their use in various fields. For example, they are used by smart energy systems for the physical synchronization of sensor data as well. Physical synchronization of data uses an Arduino or ESP board and is required to process and store the received data by the server part.

The Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) and User Datagram Protocol (UDP) are widely known transport layer protocols for the physical data synchronization. However, there are problems with the use of these protocols [1], namely fast-changing data in real-time systems. Usage of one of these protocols is a negative for the stable application work and increases the risk of data losses.

This work's aim is to develop a subsystem for real-time systems (namely "Smart energy systems") for data synchronization. The subsystem will ensure the efficiency of the UDP protocol, TCP reliability and uses Reliable UDP (RUDP) protocol [2] to solve the problem.

The tasks of the developed subsystem, which consists of a server and a client on the side of the Arduino board with sensors, are reading data specified by the system user; reliable transmission of messages between the server and the client using sockets for work according to the RUDP protocol; ensuring the most optimal delivery of messages in case of packet loss.

The implementation of the RUDP network protocol in the subsystem solves network problems with packet delay, loss, and duplication in the most optimal way during real-time synchronization of sensor and server data and reduces the load on bandwidth.

SUBSYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Smart energy systems belong to real-time systems and are based on control with a high-reliability level of technical characteristics of processes [3]. In the literature, there are general approaches to the construction of such systems using some protocols for data transmission [4]. However, unlike systems with streaming video, which have already been explored [5], in the literature, there is no description of real-time systems, which includes the smart energy systems using the RUDP protocol.

Therefore, the developed subsystem will provide real-time smart energy systems efficiency and reliability based on the RUDP protocol.

The architectural basis [6] of the subsystem - client-server. This architecture encompasses distributed systems that involve client-server interaction. A simpler form of the client-server system - a two-tier architecture. It is usually a server application to which clients connect through requests. The server has authoritarian access to the information and provides it in response to requests. An example of this architecture is a GUI application for exchanging data with business logic (database or dedicated server).

In the developed system communication between the server and the client is adjusted at the expense of a subsystem of messages. The key difference between the client and the server here is the processing of different types of messages and different approaches in work preparation.

The developed system was performed using ESP 8266 Nodemcu v3. Wi-Fi libraries were used to transfer data from the ESP card (or Arduino). The ESP8266 module can operate in access point mode and workstation mode, as well as in both modes at the same time. Typically, the access point has a network connection and provides Internet access to the device. Multiple workstations on a local network can communicate through an access point. Each device has its own unique 48-bit MAC address on the network.

To distinguish one access point from another, they have a network identifier called the Service Set Identifier (SSID), a network name that is up to 32 characters long.

In Fig. 1 shows a BME280 test sensor which was used to obtain data on humidity, temperature and atmospheric pressure. In particular, the temperature measurement range with the sensor is from -40 to +85 °C with an accuracy of 0.01 °C.

The sensor supports two interfaces - I2C and SPI [7], in particular, SPI was used in the subsystem. SPI - serial peripheral interface - is a full-duplex synchronous serial communication protocol used for short-distance communication. Since the reliability of data transmission is a priority in the context of the developed system, the choice is based on the I2C ("Inter-Integrated Circuit bus") protocol usage - a two-wire serial protocol for connecting low-speed devices [8].

Fig. 1. Example of a connected BME-280 sensor

To work with the sensor you need to install libraries – Adafruit BME280 Library and Adafruit Sensor. To flash the ESP board in the Arduino IDE, you need to find the appropriate library esp8266 by ESP8266 Community.

After connecting the BME280 sensor to the Arduino board, the BME280test from the Adafruit BME280 Library was downloaded and used as the basis for the interaction.

The subsystem was developed using the C++ programming language [9] in conjunction with the Qt Framework. Qt Creator – a cross-platform tool for both the preparation of the prototype and at the stage of developing the final product for the user. Qt Framework has a mechanism of signals and slots [10] which are handlers and are connected to the signals. Signals are thrown from a certain class which contains the declaration of this signal.

ARCHITECTURE AND SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION

The architecture of the created subsystem is shown in Fig. 2. The main application window (MainWindow) is both an element of the system layout and graphical interface. The Network layer module is responsible for network operations, socket manipulation, transmission, packet reception, and data synchronization. The Network layer module combines TCP, UDP, RUDP protocols appropriate for the client and the server. The Network layer module interacts with the Message Subsystem which encapsulates serialization/deserialization of data. The Network layer sends data as an array of bytes over the network. The Agent connects

to the server and synchronizes the registered data. The Server is responsible for receiving data from the client and transmitting it to the GUI (graphical user interface, MainWindow UI here) module. This is done through the built-in Adapter which is an intermediary between the UI and server logic, ensuring the reliability of the multithreaded system (the server is made in a separate thread).

Fig. 2. Subsystem architecture

Fig. 3 shows a sequence diagram of the subsystem. After the client preparation described above, the next step is to configure the server, in particular, the port that the server will open for listening, network protocol, and data retrieval. On the agent side, the developed library is connected, the user configures the name and password to the Wi-Fi-point which will be used to gain access.

Next, determine the code that will be used by the system to obtain data from the sensors and synchronize with the server. The reliability of the message to be synchronized, the sending interval and the flag to synchronize the sensor data at once after confirmation by the server are selected. The client sends the registered data in the form of a reliable message to the server. The agent then turns on, the client sends a request to connect to the server and receives a response, the connection is established. Then the sending of data begins in the set interval (by default - 2 seconds). The server receives these messages, sends updates to the GUI to display them, and adjust as needed. The server has the ability to configure such parameters without source code compilation of the agent board: the specified interval time, reliability (message type), data synchronization enabling flag of a particular sensor. All serialization logic is hidden from the user, but the user within the serialization can describe the appropriate methods for their message types.

The interface of the developed library for Arduino/ESP boards is designed intuitively. The messaging subsystem between the client and the server is designed using the Factory Method pattern.

Fig. 3. Sequence diagram for the subsystem

Serializing messages involves checking for the existence of an object and calling the `serialize ()` method for a specific type of message that returns the number of written bytes.

After deserialization, the message is processed by the system. To do this, a corresponding handler class based on the Singleton pattern is created to have single access to the data of this class.

The server and the client only register certain messages for processing. For example, there is no need for the client to handle messages to the server connection request because the client sends it (server-side should process it).

SUBSYSTEM WORKING MECHANISM

The `WinSock2.h` library is used to work with sockets on the Windows platform. For address and port binding `bind ()` function is used, and `send()` (for TCP) and `sendto()` (for RUDP) methods are used to send data. To obtain data `recv()` and `recvfrom()` [11] were used. There are no special problems with sending data from the client or the server. However, the data acquisition mechanism is blocking by default which creates a problem even for a multithreaded system. For example, server logic is suspended if it tries to retrieve data from a client. The server and client part which are responsible for network interaction is made in a separate thread of execution to handle it.

It should be understood that `recvfrom()` calls are used to receive messages from a socket (regardless of whether it supports the actual connection). The `recv()` call is usually used only on the socket that establishes the connection (for example, TCP).

If the socket does not receive the current packets, `recvfrom()` calls to wait for a message to arrive and block the execution of the process if the socket is blocking.

The usage of `select` or `poll` approaches can be used to receive more data during the determined time.

At each step of updating the server or the client part, the system calls the `recvfrom()` function and checks if the socket contains any data. If there is no data to process, the `sleep` instruction for the current stream (server-side) is executed for 5 ms. If there is data, we check

whether all the data for the current packet is received and pass the binary data for further conversion into the appropriate form.

The `recvfrom()` function returns any available data without waiting for the specified number of bytes required by the user for a single argument to the function. This leads to the fact that during the implementation of the stream logic for message serialization in the developed subsystem using a pointer offset, an error was received on the side of the board ESP8266. ESP8266 has restrictions on access to data through the pointer. Namely, 32-bit access must be aligned beyond the 32-bit limit and 16-bit access must be aligned beyond the 16-bit limit. To fix the `LoadStoreAlignmentCause` error you need to read or write data to a 32-bit-aligned address [12].

In the proposed subsystem this is solved by using the `memcpy` function(), which performs low-level copying of data without casting the data to a certain type (via a pointer). The function has the following signature: `void * memcpy (void * destination, const void * source, size_t num)`. The function accepts pointers to void, the function does not need to know the type the user is working with, but only knows the *destination* memory address, which must be filled with *num* bytes from the *source* memory.

Additionally, a template thread-safe queue is implemented for requests for the server. There are such requests as suspend/shut down the server, send messages. This queue is checked by the server on each update call and, if requested, processes before receiving the data.

RUDP delivers packets with the organization of two queues (for "reliable" and "unreliable" messages) and separate serial numbers for both of them, respectively. Because RUDP adds logic that controls reliable delivery, receipt, the information about the message is processed first, followed by the message itself.

A "reliable" message will be sent until we receive confirmation of receipt or the limit of available attempts is exceeded, and therefore it is necessary to keep them for some time. Also, messages with a broken order must be buffered before processing the program.

If an "unreliable" message arrives during synchronization, we set its index as the current one on the client or the server-side. To ensure the relevance of the data ignore messages whose index is less than expected (a packet that was sent later has already been received).

Because the system has two main execution threads with a graphical interface and the server separately, a processor with at least two cores is recommended. The system requires up to 15 megabytes of RAM.

To work with the server, run the file `ServerApplication.exe` and click Start Server. You can then run the agent.

The interval for sending agent sensor data on the client-side can be updated in the Sensor Interval field during server-side work.

When the client is running, the sending time is calculated for each message that the client resends. If in the first step time is equal to round trip time (RTT), i.e. sending occurs immediately, then the resending time is calculated by the equation:

$$T = RTT(2^n - 1), \quad (1)$$

where *n* is the number of the current attempt to resend the data packet. That is, the client increases the sending time exponentially and thus reduces the load on the network.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation of the developed subsystem is performed using the software application Clumsy, which causes such network problems as delay in input in milliseconds, the percentage of lost packets that are sent/received, the percentage of the duplicate packets, and lost order for received and delivered packets.

During the simulation, the subsystem work was compared using the proposed RUDP protocol and the known TCP protocol. While modelling in the software application Clumsy, duplication of packets was set to 5%, and simulation of packet loss - in the range of 15-30%.

The simulation results are shown in Figure 4. As can be seen from Fig. 4, for the TCP protocol, the maximum value was obtained when simulating the values of the time spent at 6.22 seconds to simulate packet loss of 15% (Fig. 4 a).

Fig. 4. Simulation of the average waiting time for packet loss of 15% (a, b) and 30% (c)

The results show that during this subsystem work and network parameters simulated by the application Clumsy, packets arrive. To compare performance, the subsystem also simulates work using the RUDP protocol for the same network parameters simulated by the Clumsy application. The simulation results are shown in Fig. 4b, 4c. The figure shows that the subsystem model using the RUDP protocol received a maximum value of time spent 2.03 seconds for simulation of packet loss of 15% and 3.35 seconds for simulation of packet loss of 30%.

That is, based on the simulation, it was found that the maximum value of time spent by the subsystem using the RUDP protocol is three times less than using the TCP protocol. In particular, under the above simulation conditions, the value of time spent by the subsystem is 2.03 seconds - for the RUDP protocol and 6.22 seconds – for the TCP protocol, and therefore in the future, only the RUDP protocol is used for data transmission.

Fig. 5 shows an example of the execution of the server part of the subsystem with data transmission over the RUDP protocol. In real-time mode, the following values were obtained from the sensors: temperature 24 °C, relative humidity 43%, the last received with an interval of 2 seconds was a message with an index of 31. The maximum data waiting time was 2.01 seconds without simulating packet loss.

Also, in the described subsystem, according to formula (1) exponentially set the retransmission time for each message if the subsystem loses the packet. The results of modelling the work of the subsystem in this situation are shown in Figure 6. Fig. 6 shows that the packet – 262 is resent at intervals of 0.15 seconds. After this packet is not received, it is resent after 0.35, 0.75, 1.55, 3.15 seconds, which corresponds to the time calculated according to formula (1), where $RTT = 0.05$.

Fig. 5. Execution example of server part of the subsystem

That is, the total number of retries for the packet - 262 is 6, and in total, the number of delivery attempts was set in the range of 5-8. After all, attempts are exhausted, the packet is considered lost and the other side of the subsystem is inaccessible.

```

handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 262 interval=0.15
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 262 interval=0.35
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 262 interval=0.75
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 261 interval=3.15
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 262 interval=1.55
observeSendingMessage - reliable
Sending result:24
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 263 interval=0.05
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 260 interval=6.35
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 263 interval=0.15
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 263 interval=0.35
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 263 interval=0.75
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 262 interval=3.15
handleHeartBeatTimeout: need to resent packet - 263 interval=1.55
.....
WiFi connected

```

Fig. 6. Example of packet loss and retransmission in a subsystem

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis of the literature, it is established that the TCP protocol is used to implement real-time systems.

The developed and implemented subsystem for the Smart energy systems use the RUDP protocol.

The implemented subsystem consists of an Arduino library for an agent board and a server application with a graphical interface. The subsystem encapsulates the logic of data serialization and their sending taking into account the alignment of data addresses, which facilitates the work of the user and the developer with further support of the code. The operation of the described client-server subsystem is to synchronize sensor and server data.

The subsystem is simulated using an application that simulates packet loss during transmission, duplication, and disorder. As a result of the simulation, it was found that the maximum value of time spent by the subsystem is 2.03 seconds - for the RUDP protocol and 6.22 seconds - for the TCP protocol, and therefore in the future for data transmission used only the RUDP protocol.

In case of packet loss due to unstable network work, the subsystem exponentially increases the time of resending packets. In general, the number of attempts to resend packets did not exceed 8.

Thus, the developed and implemented subsystem provides stability and reliability of the Smart energy systems using the RUDP protocol.

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